

Optimizing Material Flow Using Appropriate 3pl in Transportation

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1 Figure

- TV Hut's Supply Chain Process.
- Distributors Storage with Carrier Delivery.
- TV Hut's Push & Pull Boundary.
- TV Hut's Zone of Strategic Fit.
- Important Data of Top Two 3PL Company.

2 Abbreviation

- GPS - Global Positioning System.
- 3PL - Third-Party Logistics.
- IT - Information Technology.
- TOM - Transportation Management Systems.
- IoT - Internet of Things sensors.
- SLAs - Stringent Service Level Agreements

3 Introduction

Transportation plays a crucial role in ensuring the smooth flow of materials in Bangladesh. This South Asian nation, with its dense population and rapidly growing economy, relies heavily on efficient transportation networks for various reasons.

First, in an agrarian society, the movement of agricultural products from rural areas to urban markets is essential for food security and economic stability. Roads, railways, and waterways act as lifelines, ensuring that crops, livestock, and raw materials reach their destinations in a timely manner. Bangladesh's industrial sector, particularly the ready-made garment industry, depends on transportation to distribute raw materials and ship finished products. Disruptions in this supply chain can lead to production delays, affecting both exports and employment.

Moreover, international trade, especially with neighboring countries, relies on effective transportation links. These connections foster economic integration and are pivotal to the nation's economic growth. Bangladesh's vulnerability to natural disasters necessitates a dependable transportation infrastructure for disaster response and relief efforts. During floods or cyclones, it is vital for the swift distribution of relief materials, medical supplies, and the evacuation of at-risk populations. Transportation in Bangladesh is the linchpin of economic development, connecting rural and urban areas, facilitating trade, and ensuring disaster resilience. Investment in transportation infrastructure is imperative for the country's continued growth and prosperity.

3.1 Problem Statement:

TV Hut is presently confronted with a critical challenge in the realm of material flow and transportation. In recent times, they have encountered persistent difficulties in efficiently managing the flow of materials essential to their operations. These challenges encompass several interconnected issues, including product delivery delays, inadequate response times to customer orders, Lack of Integration and limited visibility into their supply chain.

The recurring delays in product deliveries have resulted in missed sales opportunities and customer dissatisfaction, both of which undermine their revenue and brand reputation. Their inability to respond promptly to fluctuating customer demands has led to diminished satisfaction and competitive disadvantages.

The lack of real-time visibility into our supply chain hinders our ability to monitor shipments, track performance, and manage exceptions effectively. Furthermore, our current transportation practices fall short of aligning with our sustainability commitments, posing risks to our environmental responsibility and brand integrity.

In material flow, a lack of integration in TV Hut can lead to disjointed supply chain operations. This results in inefficient transportation planning, inventory inaccuracies, delayed response to customer demands, and increased transportation costs. It hampers visibility, making it challenging to track shipments and coordinate various aspects of the supply chain. Integration is essential to optimize material flow and enhance operational efficiency.

3.2 Research Question

This report aims to explore what are the root causes of these issues, what could be the impact of these issues on TV Hut's material flow and how they can solve them to improve their material flow efficiency.

3.3 Objectives Statement:

By addressing these challenges, I aim to strengthen their retail business's competitive position and ensure sustainable growth and success and present strategic recommendations to enhance material flow efficiency, improve customer satisfaction, and realign their transportation practices with their sustainability goals.

3.4 Structure of The Report

The report unfolds in several sections, starting with the Introduction, which outlines the problem statement and sets the context for the study. The Research Questions highlight the core inquiries, investigating the root causes of the issues and their impact on TV Hut's material flow. The Objectives Statement clarifies the report's purpose, aiming to enhance material flow efficiency, customer satisfaction, and sustainability practices.

Following the introduction, the Literature Review provides a deep dive into TV Hut's operations, material flow dynamics, the role of third-party logistics (3PL), and integration strategies. Methodology details the research approach, including data collection methods, sample selection, and data analysis techniques employed during interviews with key figures at TV Hut.

In the subsequent Findings and Analysis section, the report presents insights gathered from interviews, shedding light on TV Hut's supply chain processes, network design, and challenges in material movement

and transportation. It includes detailed discussions on TV Hut's operational challenges and the impact of transportation delays on customer satisfaction.

The Recommendation section offers practical solutions for TV Hut, emphasizing strategies for network and infrastructure enhancement, scalability in contracts, technology integration, cost reduction, reliability, risk mitigation, continuous improvement, and scheduling delivery times for regional orders.

In the concluding Conclusion, the report summarizes key findings and recommendations, emphasizing the crucial role of strategic integration, technology adoption, and customer-centric approaches in overcoming material flow and transportation challenges. Throughout this report, the aim has been to provide a holistic understanding of TV Hut's challenges and offer actionable recommendations for enhancing their operational efficiency and customer service.

4 Literature Review

4.1 Company Overview

TV Hut is an electronics showroom which has products of different brands. They started their journey in 2018. Since then, they are selling TV, Fridges, air conditioners, laptops etc. Their most sold products are from Xiaomi and LG. They started their business in Dhaka at Alpana plaza's 3rd floor.(*TV HUT টিভি হাট | Dhaka*, n.d.) At the beginning of their business, they posted their products at Bikroy.com and on Facebook but after getting a huge response, they started marketing their products on different online stores and recruiting some people to promote their showroom. The Owner and Head of Operation is Naim Ahsan. He recruited his friend and previous colleague, Mr. Biswajit Shah as Head of Supply Chain. For one years, they only sold Laptops but after becoming famous, they started selling fridges, air conditioners and TV. For delivering their product, they use local courier service providers. They rented a mini warehouse in the same building. Currently they are planning to expand their business by opening more showrooms. They created and managed their website by Hasib Ahsan, who is the brother of the owner. They have partnership with Dutch Bangla Bank Limited, City Bank, BRAC Bank. Bkash, Rocket, UPay, Dhaka Bank, Islami Bank Bangladesh Limited, Mutual Trust Bank, Nagad.(*Available Payment Methods*, n.d.) Currently they have two shops, one at Alpana Plaza and another one is at Sagorika Complex.(*TV HUT*, n.d.)

Mission: TV Hut strives to earn the trust and loyalty of millions by offering top-tier after-sale service, advocating for customers, and delivering unbeatable prices with quickest delivery time.

Vision: TV Hut envisions continued expansion, diverse partnerships, and sustained excellence in service quality. They aim to provide the widest selection of electronics and accessories, both online and in-store, maintaining their position as the premier destination for electronics shopping in Bangladesh.

TV Hut has gained the trust and popularity of millions by providing industry-leading after-sale service, wise advocacy, and unbeatable prices in the market. TV Hut has many partnership affiliations with world-renowned tech brands like Samsung, Sony, LG, MI, HP, Dell, Asus, MSI and etc. ensures the quality and authenticity of products and services provided to the customer. TV Hut offers categories ranging from, Television, air conditioner, appliance, Gadgets, cameras, smart devices, monitors, and accessories with the best price in Bangladesh.(*WHY SHOP ONLINE AT TV HUT?*, n.d.)

They are constantly expanding their product range as well as improving their service quality. They offer the best selection of television, air conditioner, home appliance, gadgets, cameras, smart devices, monitors, and Accessories that customer can buy online or purchase from their outlets. They have the

largest collection of television, air conditioner, home appliances, gadgets, cameras, smart devices, monitors, and accessories in Bangladesh. Lastly, it is their highest priority here at Tvhut.com to create the best online shopping experience for every customer in Bangladesh.(WHY SHOP ONLINE AT TV HUT?, n.d.)

4.2 Understanding Material Flow

Material Flow: Material flow is dynamic systems reflecting the transport of materials between different places.(Kindler et al., 1983). Material flow refers to the movement and management of materials throughout their life cycle, with implications for resource efficiency, environmental impact, and the circular economy.

Importance of Efficient Material Flow: Effective material flow in an assembly facility leads to reduced material handling costs and increased productivity.(Ellis et al., 2010). Efficient material flow is important for flexible structures.(Farnsworth et al., 2017). Efficient material flow lowers costs, boosts productivity, reduces lead times, and enhances competitiveness, crucial for operational success in diverse industries.

4.3 Introduction to Third-Party Logistics (3PL)

What is 3PL? Third-party logistics is the term for an external logistics service provider who, typically through a contract, offers one or more logistics activities to their clients.(Fayzullayev, 2018). In the management of the supply chain, third-party logistics service providers, or 3PLs, are crucial.(Başligil et al., 2011)

Benefits of Using 3PL Services: Third-party logistics is being used more frequently for factors like bettering logistics service, cutting costs, concentrating on core competencies, specializing, and improving logistics operations. (선일석 et al., 2019). Using 3PL providers can lead to advanced customer service, greater flexibility, and cost savings.(Κουλο\acute\nuρης, 2018). Reduces logistics costs and strengthening cooperation among different transport modes through 3PL services.(Selviaridis et al., 2008)

4.4 Integration of 3PL into Material Flow

Identifying Material Flow Bottlenecks: 3PLs help identify material flow bottlenecks by analyzing data, optimizing routes, and suggesting process improvements for efficient logistics operations. Lean management principles and practices have been traditionally applied to manufacturing systems and try to make products flow through the supply chain without interruptions.(Overboom et al., 2013).

Cost Reduction: Integrating 3PL providers can lead to cost savings by eliminating the need for organizations to invest in their logistics infrastructure and staff. This cost reduction contributes to improved material flow efficiency.

Technology Integration: Many 3PL providers offer advanced technology solutions for tracking and monitoring material flow in real-time. These technologies enhance visibility, transparency, and control over the supply chain.

4.5 Collaborative Planning and Execution:

Collaborative planning and execution with a 3PL partner in efficient material flow entails aligning goals, sharing data, and jointly strategizing to optimize logistics processes. By integrating companies' objectives with the 3PL's expertise, real-time visibility, and responsive execution capabilities, a company can achieve seamless material flow, reduce bottlenecks, enhance efficiency, and meet customer demands effectively.

4.6 Overcoming Challenges

Common Challenges in Implementing 3PL Solutions: 3PL contracts can be intricate, with numerous clauses, terms, and conditions. Implementing 3PL (Third-Party Logistics) solutions can present challenges in vehicle assignment and route determination, which are critical components of efficient logistics operations. Selecting the right 3PL (Third-Party Logistics) provider is a critical step in implementing 3PL solutions, and it comes with its own set of challenges.

Strategies to Overcome Implementation Hurdles: It is important to emphasize on the importance of contract flexibility in 3PL relationships, as contracts need to accommodate changing requirements and contingencies.(David, 2016). To meet customer demands, 3PLs must have an effective distribution network. By optimizing the distribution network of 3PLs using a two-stage solution that involves vehicle assignment and route determination.(Başligil et al., 2011). Evaluating and selecting 3PL providers by a hybrid approach combining entropy, CRITIC, and ARAS methods.(Jovčić & Pr\u010duša, 2021)

5 Methodology

5.1 Sample

The qualitative data collection method involved interviews with two key figures at TV Hut: owner Naim Ahsan and supply chain manager Biswajit Shah. Their insights were crucial for this report.

5.2 Data Collection Method

Personal Experience: I used to work there since it is my cousin's business. I worked in the sales department. I used to take orders and give customer support. I saw in person their supply chain process and worked with the owner to reduce lead time.

Questionnaire: Seven open-ended questionnaire questions were used in the data collection procedure to elicit information on the supply chain, IT industry, transportation-related difficulties, and material flow problems of the company. To provide a general picture of the company's operating model, the first question sought to understand the existing supply chain process and the delivery methods employed.

Four questions that followed focused on challenges with material movement and transportation. These investigations aimed to identify any supply chain bottlenecks and logistical problems. Two more inquiries centered on IT, namely the software used for managing orders and tracking deliveries. These queries were made to pinpoint the technological devices and frameworks supporting the business' regular operations.

Overall, this approach to data collection aims to provide an in-depth examination of the business's operations and potential areas for development in transportation for good material flow was made possible by the open-ended style, which encouraged thorough and context-rich responses.

Main Research Question: How transportation issue making it hard to maintain material flow smoothly in TV Hut?

Sub-RQ 1: What factors impacts in TV Huts transportation issue?

Sub-RQ 2: What could be a perfect and cost-effective transportation method for TV Hut to keep their material flow smooth?

5.3 Procedure

Interview: I had an interview of the owner and supply chain manager. To guarantee that respondents could understand the questions, the questionnaire was carefully created in English, one of the official languages. The language was carefully chosen to maximize clarity and minimize any potential language-related difficulties. An atmosphere of ease and security was created by anonymity, encouraging honest

and open communication. The interviews took place over phone calls, which were a practical approach for enabling direct, in-person communication without geographical restrictions.

The interviewer, which was me, carefully considered and presented the questions to make sure they were set up to elicit pertinent and informative data. Seven open-ended questions on a wide range of subjects, including supply chain models and IT, comprised the survey. systems, material flow challenges, and transportation issues.

5.4 Data Analysis

I analyzed the collected data by “Narrative Analysis Method”. Narrative analysis in qualitative research is a good tool to understand how people's stories and ability to self-narrate reflect human experience. As I did an interview to collect data, narrative analysis would be best to get some idea and figure out the source of the issue through the owner and supply chain manager’s own real-life experiences in their business.

5.5 Findings And Recommendations

Upon analyzing the gathered data, I've uncovered valuable insights into the company's business operations and identified challenges related to transportation. The data sheds light on their supply chain processes, their strategic positioning, and the transportation network they employ. Additionally, it highlights specific issues within their transportation system.

To address these challenges and enhance the company's reputation and customer response rate, I have begun crafting individual recommendations. These recommendations aim to provide practical solutions that can bolster their supply chain efficiency, refine their strategic fit within the market, and tackle transportation-related problems head-on.

By implementing these recommendations, the company can potentially optimize their operations, reduce transportation bottlenecks, and ensure timely deliveries. This, in turn, can enhance their reputation for reliability and customer satisfaction. It's a step towards strengthening their competitive edge in the market, building trust with customers, and ultimately fostering business growth. The comprehensive approach to problem-solving and strategic improvement is designed to create a positive ripple effect throughout their business operations.

5.6 Research Time Horizon

The total process of taking an interview, contacting the personnel for an interview, arranging questions and deciding the mode of interview took two weeks to complete.

6 Findings And Analysis

6.1 A Typical Operation of TV Hut

Upon conducting data analysis, the intricacies of TV Hut's supply chain process have come to light. Initially, products from diverse brand distributors find their way to TV Hut's basement warehouse, utilizing the distributors' own transportation networks. This strategic warehouse placement beneath their showroom optimizes space. Embracing the digital realm, TV Hut strategically markets its products online, both on its platforms and external websites, leading to a substantial influx of online orders. Additionally, customers physically visit the showroom, placing orders in person. Once orders are received, TV Hut promptly dispatches products, employing local courier services for deliveries. The decision to collaborate with local couriers, rather than invest in a dedicated vehicle fleet, is guided by the need to evade high maintenance costs and space constraints. This agile approach ensures efficient order fulfillment. TV Hut swiftly moves products from distributors to customers, emphasizing speed and customer satisfaction. The entire process, seamlessly integrating distributor partnerships, online marketing, and local courier collaborations, reflects TV Hut's astute adaptation in the modern retail landscape.

6.2 TV Hut's Supply Chain Flow

By interviewing the 3 key position holders, I gathered information about their supply chain process (figure 1) and some insights regarding their transportation problem in optimizing material flow.

6.3 TV Hut's Network Design

One notable aspect highlighted in the interview was the company's use of a "Distributor storage with carrier delivery" distribution network design (Figure 2). This model involves receiving finished products from various factories, carefully managing inventory levels in the warehouse, and processing customer orders, primarily from online marketplaces. The interviewee explained that this model was crucial for balancing inventory to meet customer demand without overstocking. However, it was also revealed that the company predominantly receives customer orders for large products such as TVs and air conditioners, which are primarily located outside of Dhaka, the company's main market. The company's sales and order fulfillment teams take and process customer orders.

Figure 2 - Distributor Storage With Carrier Delivery.

6.4 TV Hut's Pull & Push Boundaries

Upon receiving an order from the customer, TV Hut retrieves the necessary products from its inventory. This stage is their “Push & Pull” boundary (figure 3). Then products are packed for delivery, and delivery labels are generated. To deliver the products to customers, they use local courier services.

Figure 3 - TV Hut's Pull & Push Boundary.

6.5 TV Hut's Zone of Strategic Fit

They get four or five orders every week for TV, Fridge and Air Conditioner. Most of the orders for these big products come from outside of Dhaka. Inside Dhaka they get most of the orders for laptops and mobile phones. Their sales team response as soon as possible to the customer and sent it to the courier service company to deliver. TV Hut also handles their customers' complaints nicely and takes back products if they are defective. Their position in the zone of strategic fit is also shown (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - TV Hut's Zone of Strategic Fit.

6.6 Tracking Material Flow

They use “SAP Inventory Manager” to track how much inventory is left, which product is sold and track the movement of materials using mobile devices with scanning functionality. Sometimes the customer calls them to get information about their product delivery status.

6.7 Delay in Delivery and Route Inefficiencies

Transportation delays, route inefficiencies can disrupt material flow, leading to production delays, stock outs, or increased lead times. Transportation-related issues, such as late deliveries eroding customer satisfaction and harming TV Hut's reputation. Sometimes the customers complain about the delay, and they want to get their products in 1 day since most of the companies are doing that inside Dhaka district, but because the local courier service providers have a fix schedule, they cannot deliver products the same day. The customers outside of Dhaka are ok with the delay of 2/3 days since business entities like theirs are doing the same in delivering products outside of Dhaka district. But the method TV Hut uses to deliver their products sometimes requires 4/5 days which makes the customers cancel the order sometimes. It is creating a bad reputation. The local courier service providers have specific routes and areas where they will deliver. It hampers TV Hut since they get orders from different areas of the country. Sometimes they must cancel some huge profitable orders just because of inefficient rout problem.

6.8 Hampers Material Flow:

TV Hut grapples with a critical challenge which is the unpredictable and unspecified delivery times provided by their local courier service. This issue cascades into numerous problems, including orders getting stuck, a lack of clarity in tracking product deliveries, and the looming threat of inventory overload.

The repercussions are dire, as dissatisfied customers often cancel orders due to tardy deliveries, causing a dent in both reputation and profitability

7 Recommendation

7.1 Delay Management:

For TV Hut, a small business, I recommend leveraging a Third-Party Logistics (3PL) provider to reduce transportation delays. By outsourcing logistics to a reliable 3PL, TV Hut can benefit from their expertise, network, and resources. This can lead to optimized route planning, better inventory management, and efficient order fulfillment. Additionally, the 3PL can offer real-time tracking and monitoring, helping to identify and address delays promptly. Overall, integrating a 3PL into their logistics strategy can enhance efficiency, minimize delays, and ultimately improve customer satisfaction, vital for a small business's success.

7.2 Network Mood and Infrastructure

Incorporating a multi-modal network and flexible infrastructure into TV Hut's third-party logistics (3PL) transportation strategy is recommended. Utilize a range of transportation modes, including bicycles for urban deliveries, motorcycles for speedy courier services, and trucks for larger products. This diversified approach enhances delivery options, optimizing last-mile logistics. Moreover, invest in adaptable infrastructure such as strategically located urban distribution hubs and warehousing facilities. This ensures efficient transit, reduces congestion, and improves order fulfillment speed. By embracing a multi-modal network and flexible infrastructure, your 3PL operations become agile, responsive to changing demands, and capable of providing comprehensive transportation solutions to meet your customers' diverse needs. The important data using 3PL (Top 2 companies) is shown in (Figure 5).

Outside Dhaka	Truck		Inside Dhaka	Cycle/Bike	
	RedX	Steadfast Courier		RedX	Pathao Courier
Diesel Cost	On RedX	On Steadfast	Diesel Cost	On RedX	On Pathao
Tracking App	✓	✓	Tracking App	✓	✓
Maintanace Cost	On RedX	On Steadfast	Maintanace Cost	On RedX	On Pathao
Delivery Area	Specefic District of BD	Specefic District of BD	Delivery Area	Inside Dhaka District	Inside Dhaka District
Delivery Time	2/3 Days	2/3 Days	Delivery Time	1 Day	1 Day
Product Safety Cost	On RedX	On Steadfast	Product Safety Cost	On RedX	On Pathao
Driver Cost	On RedX	On Steadfast	Driver Cost	On RedX	On Pathao
Payment	After Delivery	After Delivery	Payment	After Delivery	After Delivery

Figure 5 - Important Data of Top Two 3PLcompanies

7.3 Scalability and Flexibility in contract:

In a third-party logistics (3PL) contract, scalability and flexibility are critical components to accommodate evolving business needs. Establish clear terms for adjusting logistics services, capacity, and pricing in response to changes in shipment volumes, seasonal demands, or unforeseen circumstances. Specify lead times for modifications and integrate technology systems for seamless adaptation. Include performance monitoring mechanisms to assess the 3PL's ability to scale and meet service level agreements. Additionally, outline contingency plans and exit strategies to ensure continuity of service during disruptions or contract termination. A well-structured contract balances stability with adaptability, enabling efficient logistics operations aligned with your evolving requirements.

7.4 Technology Integration:

I recommend embracing new technology integration when partnering with a third-party logistics (3PL) provider in transportation. Leverage cutting-edge solutions such as Transportation Management Systems (TMS), Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, and real-time tracking to optimize logistics operations. These technologies enhance visibility, allowing you to monitor shipments in real-time, optimize routes, and respond swiftly to disruptions. Utilize data analytics and predictive modeling for data-driven decision-making and cost reductions. Collaborate closely with your 3PL to seamlessly integrate these tools into your supply chain processes, ensuring a competitive edge, operational efficiency, and improved customer satisfaction while adapting to the evolving tech-driven logistics landscape.

7.5 Cost Reduction:

To achieve cost reduction through third-party logistics (3PL) in transportation, consider these recommendations. First, collaborate closely with TV Hut's 3PL provider to identify cost-saving opportunities, such as route optimization, load consolidation, and efficient inventory management. Leverage their expertise to negotiate favorable carrier rates and access their economies of scale. Implement advanced technology, such as Transportation Management Systems (TMS) and real-time tracking, to minimize inefficiencies. Regularly review and analyze performance data to make data-driven decisions that lead to cost reductions. A strategic partnership with a 3PL can significantly lower operational expenses, increase efficiency, and improve TV Hut's bottom line while maintaining service quality.

7.6 Ensure Reliability and Consistency:

When engaging a third-party logistics (3PL) provider in transportation, prioritize reliability and consistency. Define stringent service level agreements (SLAs) that outline performance expectations, on-time deliveries, and shipment accuracy. Establish transparent communication channels to promptly

address any issues and maintain trust with customers. Consistently meet or exceed SLAs to build a reputation for dependable service, ensuring customers can rely on timely deliveries. Use the 3PL's expertise to navigate peak seasons or market fluctuations without compromising quality. By emphasizing reliability and consistency, Tv Hut can enhance their brand's image, cultivate customer loyalty, and strengthen their position in the market.

7.7 Risk Mitigation:

To boost profits through third-party logistics (3PL) in transportation, prioritize risk mitigation. Begin by partnering with a reputable 3PL provider with a strong track record in risk management. Collaborate on developing a robust risk assessment and mitigation strategy. This should include contingency plans for supply chain disruptions, weather-related events, and market fluctuations. Implement real-time tracking and monitoring systems to proactively identify and address potential risks. Diversify transportation modes and routes to reduce dependency on a single source. By effectively managing risks in collaboration with TV Hut's 3PL partner, they can minimize costly disruptions, enhance supply chain resilience, and ultimately, increase profitability.

7.8 Continuous Improvement:

To ensure customer satisfaction in a third-party logistics (3PL) strategy, prioritize continuous improvement. Regularly assess and enhance processes, from order placement to delivery. Implement feedback mechanisms and customer surveys to gather insights and identify areas for enhancement. Collaborate closely with TV Hut's 3PL provider to set performance metrics and KPIs that align with customer expectations. Utilize data analytics to monitor and analyze performance, making data-driven adjustments. Engage in proactive problem-solving to address issues promptly. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement, TV Hut's 3PL strategy becomes customer-centric, delivering higher service quality, better responsiveness, and ultimately, heightened customer satisfaction.

7.9 Scheduling Delivery Time Accordingly Regional orders:

Scheduling delivery times for regional orders is a logistical strategy that involves efficiently planning and coordinating the transportation of goods within a specific geographic area. It entails optimizing delivery routes, considering factors like distance, traffic, and customer time windows. Effective scheduling also requires real-time monitoring, communication with drivers, and contingency planning for unforeseen delays. Overall, regional order scheduling is crucial for balancing operational efficiency with customer satisfaction while delivering products or services regionally.

8 Conclusion

This report delves into the critical role of transportation and material flow optimization in the context of TV Hut's supply chain operations. It underscores the historical and contemporary significance of transportation, especially in a globalized world where supply chains have become increasingly complex and interconnected. The report highlights the various challenges and opportunities within TV Hut's transportation and material flow processes, including the use of third-party logistics (3PL) providers, technology integration, and cost reduction strategies.

The recommendations provided in this report emphasize the need for adaptability, scalability, and technological innovation to enhance material flow efficiency. Collaboration with 3PL providers, coupled with flexible contracts, can lead to cost reductions and improved service quality. Furthermore, embracing technology integration, reliable service, risk mitigation, and a continuous improvement mindset can strengthen TV Hut's competitive position and customer satisfaction.

By addressing these key areas, TV Hut can not only optimize its material flow and transportation but also fortify its resilience in the face of disruptions, ultimately enhancing profitability and customer loyalty. This research report serves as a roadmap for TV Hut to navigate the complexities of the modern supply chain landscape while staying competitive and customer centric.

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9 Appendix A: Interview Question:

1. Can you provide an overview of TV Hut's current material flow processes within the supply chain, particularly in relation to transportation?
2. What are the major challenges or bottlenecks you've encountered in material flow optimization?
3. What are the primary objectives and goals of TV Hut in managing material flow, and how do transportation-related challenges affect these goals?
4. Could you describe specific challenges or issues that TV Hut has encountered in material flow due to transportation, such as delays, inefficiencies, or disruptions?
5. How does TV Hut currently track and monitor the movement of materials from their warehouse to customers? Are there any gaps in visibility?
6. What transportation modes (e.g., road, rail, air, sea) does TV Hut primarily rely on for material movement, and have there been any challenges specific to certain modes?
7. What supply chain management software have you used? .

10 Appendix B: Interview Transcript:

Me: Good day and thank you for taking the time to share insights about TV Hut's supply chain and transportation operations. To begin, could you provide an overview of TV Hut's current material flow processes within the supply chain, particularly in relation to transportation?

Naim Ahsan (Owner): Of course, it's my pleasure. TV Hut operates as a distributor of electronic goods, particularly TVs, refrigerators, and air conditioners. Our supply chain involves receiving finished products from various factories and storing them in our warehouse. We carefully manage inventory to meet customer demand without overstocking. Orders primarily come through online platforms. Once we receive an order, we retrieve the products from our inventory.

Biswajit Shah (Supply Chain Manager): We often get four or five orders a week for larger products like TVs, fridges, and air conditioners. These larger orders mostly come from areas outside Dhaka. Inside Dhaka, we primarily receive orders for laptops and mobile phones.

Me: What are the major challenges or bottlenecks you've encountered in material flow optimization?

Biswajit Shah (Supply Chain Manager): The main challenge we face is in meeting delivery time expectations. Customers often request delivery within a day, especially within Dhaka. However, our ability to deliver daily is constrained by the local courier service provider's schedule.

Naim Ahsan (Owner): The situation is different for orders outside Dhaka. These customers are generally more understanding of a 2–3-day delivery timeframe since most businesses in our category follow similar practices.

Me: What are the primary objectives and goals of TV Hut in managing material flow, and how do transportation-related challenges affect these goals?

Naim Ahsan (Owner): Our primary objectives include ensuring smooth and efficient material movement, minimizing delays and disruptions, reducing transportation costs, and improving profitability. We also aim to meet customer expectations by delivering products on time and in good condition.

Biswajit Shah (Supply Chain Manager): Transportation challenges can significantly affect our ability to meet these objectives. Delays, route inefficiencies, and maintenance costs can disrupt material flow, leading to production delays and stockouts, which, in turn, erode customer satisfaction.

Me: Can you describe specific challenges or issues that TV Hut has encountered in material flow due to transportation, such as delays, inefficiencies, or disruptions?

Naim Ahsan (Owner): One of the most significant issues is the local courier service providers do not deliver to every area of the country. Because of this, we had to cancel some of our big orders.

Biswajit Shah (Supply Chain Manager): Customers sometimes complain about delivery delays, especially when they want their products within a day. While we understand these expectations, it's challenging to meet them given the constraints we face.

Me: How does TV Hut currently track and monitor the movement of materials from their warehouse to customers? Are there any gaps in visibility?

Biswajit Shah (Supply Chain Manager): We use the "SAP Inventory Manager" to track inventory levels, sales, and material flow.

Me: What transportation modes (e.g., road, rail, air, sea) does TV Hut primarily rely on for material movement, and have there been any challenges specific to certain modes?

Naim Ahsan (Owner): We primarily rely on road transportation for material movement. The challenges in road transportation, as I mentioned earlier, are delays and route issues.

Me: Thank you for your valuable time and co-operation.

11 Appendix C: Personal Reflection:

This study experience has deepened my awareness of the difficult balance between effectiveness, customer satisfaction, and business profitability in addition to improving my understanding of supply chain dynamics. Knowing that these findings might influence how TV Hut operates in the future made it a satisfying undertaking to formulate suggestions that combine theory and pragmatism.

I feel quite accomplished as I end this study because I feel like I have made a significant contribution to the conversation on contemporary supply chain management. My conviction in the transformative potential of research and its capacity to foster positive change in the commercial environment has been strengthened because of this journey.